
100. The Fermi Paradox

I TOUCHED ON the Fermi paradox in my essay #55. It refers to the question famously posed by the eminent nuclear physicist Enrico Fermi in 1950: *'If other advanced civilisations exist, where are they?'*. Alternatively formulated as *'If alien civilisations existed, they would be here'*, or as the 'Great Silence' problem, it is a deceptively simple question that presents a challenge for theories assuming a naturalistic origin of life and intelligence.

Following my last two essays on the nature of 'Boyajian-type stars', and the search for Dyson spheres, I wanted to look at it in a slightly wider context... even though it is not immediately linked to new Gaia results.

SEARCHES FOR LIFE, and more so *intelligent* life, are faced with the question: 'what is life?' Interestingly, despite abundant empirical data, there is no generally accepted definition. In biology, it is considered a characteristic of organisms that display all, or most of, a set of phenomena including metabolism, growth, adaptation, reproduction, regulation, and response to stimuli.

An alternative came through NASA's efforts to create a working definition for its astrobiology programmes. This defined life as: 'a self-sustaining chemical system capable of Darwinian evolution'. Nonetheless, difficulties of definition aside, intuitive concepts of life and intelligence are probably sufficiently developed to allow relevant research to advance.

PROGRESS IN UNDERSTANDING the *origin* of life on Earth is a big and complex story – involving chemistry, biology, and geophysics (and many hypotheses) – and based on the fact that life on Earth is dependent on the specialised chemistry of carbon and water. Indeed, complex organic molecules are found widely in the solar system and beyond, and it is these that are considered to have provided the starting materials. Candidates for first life include hydrothermal vents and extremophiles.

A few relevant timescales are: 13.7 Gyr for the origin of the Universe, 4.5 Gyr for the origin of our solar system, 3.5 Gyr for the first life forms, and 300 000 for modern humans. And we should note that many other stars are much older, while many others are much younger.

FIVE MAJOR STAGES of the origin of life have been suggested: starting from inorganic molecules and the synthesis of the simplest organic building blocks, continuing through self-organisation into more complex molecules, leading to the first reaction pathways, the spontaneous aggregation into macrostructures and, eventually, a system capable of being shifted from chemical equilibrium, maintaining homeostasis (regulation) and undergoing evolution.

But the processes are challenging: Howland (OUP, 2000) suggested that believing that a living organism would inevitably arise through self-assembly is *'... similar to a tornado descending on a junkyard and producing, by self-assembly, a jet airliner'*.

IT IS WORTH stressing that there is, today, no clear evidence for life beyond Earth. Elsewhere in the solar system, the present status is broadly as follows. In the absence of liquid water, neither the Moon nor Mercury are considered to have ever been habitable. Venus and Mars are both considered uninhabitable today, although both may have been habitable earlier in their history.

Amongst the various icy moons of Jupiter (Europa, Ganymede and Callisto), Saturn (Titan and Enceladus), and Neptune (Triton), liquid water oceans may exist beneath surface ice layers, so providing possible habitats for life. And there are various plans for space missions to probe some of them for possible biosignatures.

IN THE ONGOING search for life on exoplanets, spectroscopy is considered a key tool. Which spectral features are best targeted tends to rest on the idea that life is C/H₂O based. For example, O₂ may be a possible but not necessary by-product, with O₂ and O₃ absorption considered as promising biosignatures. With CH₄ resulting from anaerobic decomposition of organic matter, the (high disequilibrium) existence of both CH₄ and O₂ may be strong evidence for the presence of life.

Wider considerations of this type motivated the ESA Darwin and NASA TPF missions to target *infrared* observations for key spectral lines, such as H₂O at 6–8 μm , CH₄ at 7.7 μm , O₃ at 9.6 μm , and CO₂ at 15 μm .

THE DRAKE EQUATION was formulated by Frank Drake (1961) as an aid in trying to estimate the number of technical civilisations in the Galaxy today, at or beyond our technology level. It takes the form:

$$N = R_{SF} \times f_p \times n_e \times f_i \times F_i \times F_c \times L$$

where R_{SF} is the star-formation rate averaged over the Galaxy lifetime; f_p is the fraction of stars with planetary systems; n_e is mean number of planets in such systems suitable for life; f_i is the fraction of such planets on which life originates; F_i is the fraction of such planets on which 'intelligence' develops; F_c the fraction of such planets developing a communicative phase; and L is the mean lifetime of such technical civilisations.

Our ability to attach plausible probabilities to each of these terms decreases (strongly) down this chain. Estimates for N accordingly vary widely, from 10^6 (Sagan 1966), to much less than 1 (Barrow & Tipler, 1986).

THE SEARCH for intelligent life, SETI, is meanwhile motivated by the belief that intelligent life is likely to emerge under conditions similar to Earth's.

Amongst past or present searches are those undertaken at radio wavelengths, including an all-sky survey at 1–10 GHz funded by US Congress until 1993, and later continued as Project Phoenix (using the Parkes 64-m, Green Bank 140-ft, and the Arecibo 300-m); the Allen Telescope Array (42 antennae operational since 2007); and Yuri Milner's (2016, 100M\$) 'Breakthrough Listen' initiative using the Parkes and Green Bank telescopes.

Optical searches have been made based on intercepting targeted interstellar laser communications, arguing that pulses of 1 TW over many pico-seconds might be detectable across our Galaxy.

Others are being made for anomalous celestial objects such as Oumuamua (discovered in 2017, #25), and Boyajian's star (in 2015, #98), and even signatures of alien engineering (e.g. Dyson spheres, #99). And I referred to a couple of the most renowned 'false alarms' in essay #55, including the episode during the discovery of pulsars in 1967, and the 'Wow' signal of 1977.

WHAT MAKES Earth habitable in the first place? The answer appears to be a remarkable combination of many fortuitous circumstances. Amongst them, our Sun appears to be a particularly suitable host star (not too massive, not too light), and one without superflares.

Our Earth is at the 'perfect' distances from the Sun, resulting in liquid surface water, and it placing us not only in the 'habitable zone', but also in the 'continuously habitable zone' over billions of years. Earth is also of a 'perfect' mass – less massive planets retain no atmospheres, while much more massive can become gaseous – while massive enough for plate tectonics, which reprocesses CO_2 to CaCO_3 .

It has an atmosphere which resulted from out-gassing and nebular gas capture, and possesses liquid water resulting from cometary impacts early in the Solar System formation, the resulting water oceans are being not too shallow, and not too deep. Relatively few major asteroids impacts have occurred in the past billion years.

Meanwhile our Moon (originating from an early giant impact) appears to stabilise Earth's spin axis, assisting climate stability. And Jupiter, in its outer orbit, acts as an attractor for potentially impacting asteroid. There have been no nearby/recent supernovae (which could wipe out life), while the metal content of our solar system, including supplies of rare-earth elements, is also auspicious. The list of favourable 'coincidences' goes on.

AND SO TO THE Fermi paradox: if alien civilisations exist, as is presumably quite likely, where are they?

Existence probabilities are largely founded on arguments of scale, which run broadly, and in order of increasing uncertainty: (a) that the Sun is relatively young, and there are billions of stars in the Galaxy significantly older; (b) that some are likely to have Earth-like planets which, if Earth is typical, may develop intelligent life; (c) some of these are likely to develop interstellar travel; (d) under plausible assumptions, including a civilisation's average lifetime, they are likely to have explored or colonised the Galaxy on time scales of 1–100 Myr.

The paradox then arises as the contradiction between probability estimates of the existence of such civilisations, and the absence of evidence either for intelligent life elsewhere in the Galaxy (via detected 'signals'), or actual visits (e.g., of alien space probes).

ONE INTERPRETATION of the Fermi paradox is that alien civilisations simply do not exist. In this scenario, Earth is unique (within the Galaxy, or Universe) in harbouring intelligence. This may be because, even though life appeared early in Earth's geological history, it may nonetheless be a highly improbable occurrence.

Contrasting with the uniqueness view, many other explanations for the absence of 'visits' have been put forward. They can be grouped as physical (some fundamental difficulty makes space travel impossible); sociological (extraterrestrials have not visited Earth, either by choice, or due to the limited longevity of technological civilisations); temporal (advanced civilisations have arisen only recently, with insufficient time to reach us); or visits have occurred, but are not presently observed.

Today, resolution of the paradox remains unclear. It may be that intelligent life on Earth is unique in the Galaxy. Or it may be that the failure of searches to detect advanced civilisations is subject to so many interpretations as to be, at present, without significance.

Or it may signal bleak prospects for Earth in terms of impending natural or human-driven catastrophes.